

Image-Based Glucose Concentration Detection in Liquids using Refractometer and Grayscale-RGB Processing

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Abstract

Excessive sugar consumption is a key contributor to the increasing global prevalence of diabetes mellitus, necessitating the development of low-cost, accurate, and non-invasive sugar detection technologies. This study presents a novel image-processing-based prototype that integrates a handheld analog refractometer with a digital microscope camera and Python-based processing for the estimation of glucose concentration in liquid samples. The system captures images of refractometer scale readings and processes them using both grayscale and RGB color space transformations to enhance visual clarity and interpretability.

The methodology was tested using 30 laboratory-prepared glucose solutions and 15 commercial beverage samples. Each sample's refractometer image was analyzed using Python scripts to extract and compare grayscale intensity and RGB channel clarity. The grayscale transformation consistently provided superior visual results, enabling clearer observation of scale demarcations compared to individual RGB channels.

Quantitative analysis showed that the system achieved up to 85% agreement with manual mass-based calculations. For instance, a 1g glucose sample in 10 ml of water yielded a 15% reading on the refractometer, compared to 9% by manual computation. Results from commercial beverages revealed inconsistencies between labeled sugar contents and actual refractometric readings, highlighting the system's potential for quality control applications.

The proposed prototype demonstrates high potential for practical use in low-resource environments. It enables semi-automated, visual quantification of sugar content and supports future developments toward portable, real-time, and non-invasive glucose monitoring tools in the domains of food safety, public health, and biomedical diagnostics.

Keywords: *glucose detection, grayscale transformation, image processing, python prototype refractometer, RGB analysis*